

Shock Reflection Behavior in High-Speed Rarefied Gas Flow

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Abstract

The behavior of shock wave reflection in different levels of flow rarefaction is investigated using the Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) method. For this, an internal supersonic Argon gas flow over a sudden ramp geometry is considered. DSMC simulations are performed via dsmcFoam module of OpenFOAM package. After verification of shock reflection phenomenon in continuum limit with the CFD simulations and analytical relations, the effect of different levels of flow rarefaction is examined using decreasing the upstream flow density. The simulation results indicate that flow rarefaction leads to thickening of both incident and reflected shockwaves. It is revealed that rarefaction effect is more obvious on the reflected shock wave with respect to the incident one. One can observe a curved shock profile at the incident points, where a straight shockwave is expected in continuum flow condition. We detect non-equilibrium flow regions near the incident points where non-equilibrium effects lead to curved shock profile.

Keywords: *Rarefied Gas Flow - Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) - Shockwave Reflection - dsmcFoam - Continuum Gas Flow*

1. Introduction

Shockwave reflection in rarefied gas flows is a complex phenomenon relevant in high-speed aerodynamics, hypersonic flows, and vacuum system design. The study focuses on the interaction of shockwaves with boundaries, flow fields, and reflected waves in low-density regimes where the continuum assumption breaks down. Rarefied flows are characterized by the Knudsen number (Kn), which measures the degree of rarefaction, necessitating computational and theoretical approaches like the Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) method and Boltzmann equation-based models.

Bird [1] showed that in highly rarefied flows, shockwaves are not sharp discontinuities but have finite thickness due to reduced collisional effects. Nance and Hassan [2] extended these studies, examining shockwave interactions with surfaces and highlighting the influence of wall accommodation coefficients. Titarev *et al.* [3] explored the reflection of a uniform supersonic rarefied-gas flow incident on a wall with an orifice. Using the kinetic S-model, they examined the influence of the orifice on the reflection nature, the velocity of the reflected shock wave, and the formation of a gas jet flowing into a vacuum.

Their findings highlighted the complex interactions between the shockwave and the orifice, which significantly affect the reflection characteristics. Takata *et al.* [4] investigated the effects of rarefaction on shock reflections using molecular dynamics simulations. Their work revealed significant deviations in density and temperature profiles at shock boundaries, influencing reflection behavior. Holtz and Muntz [5] examined velocity distribution functions near shock boundaries, showing anisotropy in molecular velocities, which plays a critical role in shaping reflected shock characteristics.

Zuppardi and Boffa [6] focused on shockwave interaction with walls in rarefied conditions, highlighting how surface roughness and thermal accommodation coefficients affect reflection patterns. Gardner and Agarwal [7] studied the influence of rarefaction on shock reflection over hypersonic forebodies, focusing on how it affects heat transfer and pressure distribution. Using a combination of DSMC method and modified Navier-Stokes equations, the study reveals that rarefaction significantly alters the thermal and pressure characteristics of the shock reflection process.

In the current research, we investigate the shock reflection behavior for a supersonic inflow channel faced with a sudden ramp. Simulation results will be performed via DSMC method under dsmcFoam package. The effect of flow rarefaction on the incident and reflected shockwave patterns is examined. Also, the pressure and temperature distributions through the incident and reflected shockwaves are considered and discussed.

2. Material and Method

2.1. Direct simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) method

The Direct Simulation Monte Carlo (DSMC) method offers a computational solution to the Boltzmann equation by directly simulating molecular processes statistically [8]. Each particle in the simulation represents a large number of real gas molecules. The flowchart of this method is illustrated below in Figure 1. The computational approach begins with the Boltzmann equation, which serves as the foundation for describing molecular behavior. As defined in equation (1) from the paper, the Boltzmann equation tracks the evolution of the velocity distribution function, accounting for both molecular movements and collisions.

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(nf) + c \frac{\partial}{\partial r}(nf) = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \int_0^{4\pi} n^2 (f'f'_1 - ff_1) c_r \sigma d\Omega dc \quad (1)$$

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2.3. dsmcFoam solver

dsmcFoam, a parallel DSMC solver, can model arbitrary geometries and multiple gas species on parallel computers. It employs various collision models, comparable to codes like MONACO and PDSC. The solver benefits from OpenFOAM's hierarchical structure, allowing users to utilize most features without extensive coding knowledge. Functions are categorized and shown in Figure 2. More details on its algorithms can be found in the referenced study.

In this study, dsmcFoam v12 has been utilized. For binary collision modeling, the Larsen Borgnakke Variable Hard Sphere (LB-VHS) model, along with Specular Reflection as the wall interaction model, have been employed.

Fig. 1: Flowchart of the DSMC algorithm

2.4. Physical specifications

In this study, a converging channel is selected as the geometry. The channel has a length of 1.7 m, a height of 0.5m, and a width of 1m. Since the geometry is 2D, there is only 1 cell in the width of the channel. The boundary conditions for this case are: velocity inlet at the left, pressure outlet at the right, symmetry at the top and forehead of the ramp at the bottom, and a wall with a turn angle of 10° at the ramp. The viscous model selected is Laminar with a density-based steady-state solver.

The inlet conditions are a velocity of 736.5 m/s at a temperature of 150K, forming a supersonic inlet at Mach 3.2 for Argon gas. In the DSMC, inlet and outlet have Free Stream boundary conditions. The pressure is considered to be 2atm at the inlet of the near-continuum case.

After calculating the collision frequency, the time step for the DSMC solver is obtained to be 1.0×10^{-8} s. For the continuum limit case, the nEquivalent-Particles is equal to 1.515×10^{20} , and the Number Density is 9.79×10^{25} . For the near-continuum case, the density is reduced by 10^{-5} order. Therefore, the first case is named

1.0×10^{-5} . After this, the rarefaction of the rest of the cases increases step by step as 0.5×10^{-5} , 0.25×10^{-5} , 1.0×10^{-6} , 0.5×10^{-6} , 0.25×10^{-6} .

Fig. 2: Directory of dsmcFoam solver

3. Solver Verification

To verify the solver's reliability and capability in this case, a verification with the commercial solver Fluent 24.0, as well as analytical relations and results, has been conducted. The simulation grids used for both CFD and DSMC are shown in Figure 3, which contains 21,000 structured cells. It should be noted that adaptive mesh refinement has been applied to the CFD case to improve the precision of shock capturing.

Fig. 3: Computational domain and employed grid for CFD (a-b) and DSMC (c) calculations

Since this study compares the results of shock reflection behavior from the continuum to the rarefied regime, and the NS equations are valid in the continuum regime, the verification has been carried out for a near-continuum regime. A comparison between Mach number contours can be seen in Figure 4 below, which shows an approximately exact agreement among analytical, CFD, and DSMC solutions (wave angle of 27°). Additionally, the Mach numbers, reflection, and location of shock in the continuum (CFD) and near-continuum (DSMC) solutions show adequate and precise similarity.

4. Results and Discussions

In this section, the effect of rarefaction is studied. As mentioned in the Physical Specifications section, six cases with different levels of rarefaction are selected for investigation.

Fig. 4: Contours of Mach number obtained by CFD (upper) and DSMC (lower). Analytical solution is indicated by dashed lines.

Figure 5 represents and compares Mach number contours of all cases. It can be seen that as the level of rarefaction increases, the shape of the first oblique shock changes and thickens. The variation in shockwave thickness is not limited to the first oblique shock; the reflection also changes similarly. These changes in the structure of shock reflection are due to the increase in molecular free path. In other words, when density decreases, molecular collisions decrease, delaying the progress of shock wave creation and, subsequently, reflection. Furthermore, it can be observed that the minimum Mach number decreases with increasing rarefaction. This indicates that the more rarefied the flow, the stronger the shockwaves.

The first theory is that, as the flow spends more time in the shock region, dissipating effects act more on the flow momentum, resulting in greater energy loss. Alternatively, the second theory suggests that, as the number of molecules diminishes with rarefaction, the effect of shockwaves applies to fewer molecules, causing a greater reduction in momentum. In other words, their inertia regarding momentum changes when passing through the shockwave decreases with reduced density.

Moreover, considering the pressure and temperature distribution for three benchmark cases of 1.0×10^{-5} , 1.0×10^{-6} , and 0.25×10^{-6} in Figures 6 and 7, the increase in shockwave thickness is evident. Figures 6 and 7 are drawn for each case at six different distance fractions from the upper wall, along straight lines in the domain. Considering the upper section of each graph, from left (red line) to right (black line), the graph starts from the top wall and extends to distances of 90%, 80%, 70%, 50%, and 25% from the top wall, respectively.

Analyzing both the P-X and T-X graphs, the thickness of shockwaves can be observed through the curvature of the line graphs. In the near-continuum case, the changes are sharp, and the sharpness of the lines represents this. In more rarefied cases, the graph lines bend and turn into curved lines, indicating a gradual change in properties.

Fig. 5: Mach number contour for all cases

This gradual change means the shockwaves have thickened. Comparing different distances from the top wall shows that this change is uniform across all domain sections.

Considering the pressure ratios and temperature ratios in four different rarefactions in Figure 8 and 9, figures show that shockwave thickness does not affect wall transport phenomena.

Fig. 6: Pressure and Temperature distribution on different distances from top wall

Fig. 7: Temperature distribution on different distances from top wall

This means that the pressure and temperature on the top wall change in one step, but at a distance of 50% from the top wall, it happens in two steps for the near-continuum case. Increasing rarefaction results in merging these steps into one step. This indicates that shockwaves are moving closer to each other due to their thickness.

The key point here is that, in the most rarefied case of 0.25×10^{-6} , when both waves are merged, their behavior tends to resemble a normal shock. This is evident in the maximum temperature ratio in this case, which are considerably higher than in the rest of the cases.

Pressure Ratio

Fig. 8: Pressure ratio for different rarefaction levels at top wall and 50% distance from top wall

Nomenclature

P	Pressure
P0	Initial pressure
T	Temperature
T0	Initial temperature
X	X-Coordinate
f	Velocity distribution function (before collision)
f_1	Velocity distribution function (before collision, partner molecule)
f'	Velocity distribution function (after collision)
f'_1	Velocity distribution function (after collision, partner molecule)
n	Number density
r	Space vector

Temperature Ratio

Fig. 9: Temperature ratio for different rarefaction levels at top wall and 50% distance from top wall

5. Conclusions

The behavior of shock wave reflection in rarefied gas flow was investigated DSMC method. It was shown that flow rarefaction leads to thickening of both incident and reflected shockwaves. compared to the incident shockwave, rarefaction effects are more obvious for the reflected shockwave. It was revealed that there are non-equilibrium regions near incident shockwave points where, non-equilibrium effects lead to curved shockwave instead straight one.

c Velocity space vector

c_r relative velocity between a molecule with velocity class c

Greek symbols

$\sigma d\Omega$ differential cross section for the collision of a molecule of class c

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